

Variant Effect What? Episode 1 Transcript and Show Notes

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Facilitated by the Altas of Variant Effect Alliance

Alex Nguyen Ba: Welcome to the Variants and Us podcast, a series initiated by the outreach efforts of the Atlas of Variant Effects alliance. I'm Alex, a professor at the University of Toronto, and the team: Evelina, Kortni, Adrine, and Moez, consists of scientists working at the forefront of research in the field of genetics. Our podcast began with a simple goal: to provide a voice on behalf of researchers in the field of clinical genetics and to advocate for increased awareness on rare genetic variants and diseases. To do so, we will take a deep dive into the intersection of rare disease genetics and high-throughput functional genomics.

This group came together as a volunteer, grassroots effort in 2023 after the Mutational Scanning Symposium. We wanted to understand the people, problems, and projects that drive genetics and genomics forward. We hope you'll join us on this journey.

Our first season runs the gamut of discussing the origins of disease-causing variants, to artificial intelligence in genetics, to understanding what it takes, clinically, to reclassify a Variant of Uncertain Significance to either disease-causing or benign.

This season has 6 episodes, each talking to two or three people essential for the field of variant interpretation. We are going to cover topics such as clinical genetic screening and rare disease, testing variants in large-scale, disease risk, the intercept between variants and environmental contexts, computational predictors and so much more...

Every episode, two hosts will take you on a journey to think, get informed and have fun! At the end of each episode, we are going to have this fun section where we ask silly science questions to top scientists in the field, so stay until the end to hear fire science questions.

Finally, I would like to note that this podcast focuses on a realistic portrayal of the basic and translational research behind rare diseases with the hope that it will lead to better patient care, but this podcast is not meant to be medical advice.

[Intro music plays]

Evelina Tronina: Our ability to detect variations in the human genome has greatly expanded in the last decade. Every person has 100 to 200 new mutations never seen before by science. How do we know which ones cause disease?

Kortni Kindree: Today we are speaking to three internationally recognized researchers about the connections between DNA variants, our health, and so-called 'rare genetic diseases'. To better introduce the podcast, we reached out to Dr. Stan Fields and Dr. Doug Fowler, who have made this all possible.

Evelina: Thank you Dr. Fields and Dr. Fowler for joining us today. Can you please tell us a little bit about yourselves?

Stan Fields: I'm Stan Fields. I'm a professor at the University of Washington in Seattle.

Doug Fowler: My name is Doug Fowler. I'm a professor of Genome Sciences and bioengineering at the University of Washington in Seattle.

Kortni: Dr. Fowler, you were a past postdoctoral researcher of Dr. Fields. Can you maybe tell us a little bit about your journey developing this field? How did you end up in Dr. Fields' lab?

Doug Fowler: I thought to myself, I should go to a genomics lab and go to a genomics technology lab and start learning about this part of biology that had this incredible track record of technical innovation. And so that led me to Stan, because Stan Fields is one of those sort of pioneers in using genomics to measure things about proteins.

And I interviewed in, you know, a number of other fantastic labs that were kind of in somewhat similar spaces. But the reason that I ended up joining Stan's lab was that I came for an interview and, you know that I'm not a person who loves to dress in a fancy way. And nonetheless, I felt like I really needed to, you know, show up in the interview with like a suit and a tie which I did. And, you know, Stan, I walked into his office and he said, well, that tie really looks uncomfortable, you know, do you want to take it off? And I said, you know what? I do want to take it off and I took the tie off and put it in my pocket, and that summarizes I guess Stan, he's a very warm and welcoming person, and I think that got the interview off on the right foot, and I ultimately decided to join his lab.

Stan Fields: So one story that's always been fun was that Doug told me that he wanted to be an astronaut when he grew up. And that problem was he got too tall, and you have to be within a certain height in order to be an astronaut and he outgrew it so he couldn't become an astronaut. And so maybe NASA's loss has been biology's gain.

Evelina: I've heard this a lot, many scientists wanted to explore space as children. There is something exciting about exploring the unknown or deciphering the uncertain.

Kortni: And this is a great segue into what the Variants and Us podcast is about. As we are taught in introductory biology, our DNA provides instructions to build proteins. It uses just four bases, A, C, T, and G, to create all of the proteins necessary for life. Those instructions are within our genes, where each is several hundred to several thousand bases long.

Evelina: You have probably also learned that we inherit one copy of each gene from our parents, but what you might not have learned is that you also inherit about 100 new mutations.

Mutations are produced when the DNA is copied imperfectly, and a different base is inserted into the sequence. Some mutations are harmful and have negative health consequences.

Kortni: Unfortunately, when some genes malfunction, they can cause what is called a 'genetic disease'. We refer to these genes as 'disease genes'. So how many disease genes are there? How many of us have a genetic disease? And finally, how can we tell which part of our DNA is responsible for these diseases?

Evelina: To answer these questions, we will explore how we can decipher our DNA variants with Dr. Fields, Dr. Fowler, and Dr. Costain, who you will hear about near the end of the episode.

Kortni: The human genome, which encompasses all of our DNA, contains 20 thousand genes. At least 12,000 are estimated to be involved in disease. A major challenge for the field of medical genomics is knowing which of the variants that we have are benign and which are pathogenic. Dr. Fowler, can you explain this challenge? What are these variants and how do we detect them in individuals?

Doug Fowler: Usually the person has gone to a genetics clinic but it can also happen when a person participates in a research study or decides to get their genome or a part of their genome sequenced for some other reason. And what you find when you sequence a genome is a ton of variants. And most of those variants are benign variants. They don't do anything relative to disease and a lot of them are really common benign variants that occur in a large fraction of the population. And those are unlikely to be pathogenic. But then what you end up with is this pile of thousands and thousands of rare or even private, meaning they only have ever been found in the person who got the genetic test, variants and those variants are deeply problematic.

Evelina: So what happens in these cases? What can a clinical geneticist do?

Doug Fowler: So clinicians will look at all the information they can find about that variant.

Its population frequency, we talked about that, but also like the phenotype of the person who presented at the clinic, if there's family information about the variant. You know all the information they have and they'll try to say, OK, do I think this variant is pathogenic? Is there enough evidence to say it's pathogenic? Is there enough evidence to say it's benign? And unfortunately, a lot of the time depending on the gene, it can be pretty frequently, the answer is no, there isn't enough information. And then what happens is the variant is deemed a variant of uncertain significance.

Stan Fields: And that's a huge problem in clinical genetics because so many variants are of the category of the VUS.

Kortni: Dr. Stan Fields and Dr. Doug Fowler developed a revolutionary way of determining all the disease causing mutations in the human genome. The technique they use is called a 'Multiplex Assay of Variant Effect', or MAVE, for short. Can you explain MAVEs in more detail?

Stan Fields: So MAVE is a multiplex assay of variant effects. So it's an idea where you would mutate every base in a gene or every amino acid in a protein and see what the effects are.

And the MAVE would show you the effects of each of these mutations, each of these changes.

Doug Fowler: You can contrast a MAVE with experiments that are not MAVEs. So a not MAVE experiment is you have a variant, you're interested in, just one, and you go into the lab and you test the variant's effect, maybe it's testing a variant protein and how that variant protein behaves compared to a reference or a variant cell and how it behaves to a reference sequence or maybe a variant mouse or whatever your experimental model is.

And you do that one at a time and you can test a few variants in a model.

Evelina: Scientists usually test the effect of human mutations in what they call 'model organisms', which have properties that allow them to infer what would happen in a human being. But coming back on how MAVEs work...

Doug Fowler: In a MAVE, you instead get a whole bunch of variants like maybe thousands or even tens of thousands.

And you use some of the technologies that have been developed in my lab and other labs around the world to test those variants or evaluate their effects experimentally, not one at a time but all together.

And the sort of magic or secret sauce of MAVEs is leveraging the power of high throughput DNA sequencing to read out the experimental effects of each variant in a pooled fashion.

Kortni: Proteins are composed of smaller molecules called amino acids. There are twenty amino acids in total, and they provide different chemical properties for proteins. Changes in DNA cause changes in the amino acid sequence of a protein, leading to its changing properties.

Evelina: Although we know about many disease-causing mutations, we are not even close to identifying all of them. MAVEs appear to test every mutation in a gene, even the ones we have never seen in the clinic before.

Kortni: So, what is the benefit of testing every mutation in the lab?

Stan Fields: I think we did fairly early on realize that if we thought of what the technology could do outside of protein activities and protein functions, then the place that you would see mutations in proteins, there would be lots of value in knowing what they did would be in human genetics. And so I think early on this idea of a look up table where anybody who came into the clinic and had a gene sequenced and you see a variant that many times that variant had not been functionally characterized.

And, and it would be a lot of work to go ahead one by one and build that variant.

So I think once the first mutational scan was done, I don't think it was too long after that, that the realization to us and probably lots of other people was that you could use this in clinical genetics.

Doug Fowler: Although we have only found a small fraction of the possible variants of the genome in the people we've sequenced so far, we can actually demonstrate pretty easily that if we sequence everyone on the planet, we would eventually find nearly every possible variant in the genome.

And in fact, the math says they do occur because there are 8 billion and a bit people on the planet. And we know how fast or how frequently a base in the human genome can acquire a mutation and, and become another base. If you just multiply like that rate by the size of the genome, by the number of people on the planet, then you can work out that there has to be something like 50 instances of every possible variant, compatible with life out there in the human population. And like I said, that's a dangerous number because what that means is we're just going to keep discovering more variants.

Kortni: You might be asking yourself, if everybody was sequenced could we then tell which mutation causes disease? Couldn't we just see whether a variant is more frequently associated with a disease than expected by chance? Unfortunately, because some variants are so rare, not everybody with a pathogenic variant will develop the disease, making it statistically difficult to associate the mutation to the symptoms.

Doug Fowler: And so that puts us in a challenging situation relative to interpreting the clinical consequences of those variants.

Kortni: So the goal of multiplex assays of variant effects, or MAVEs, is to test the effect for all mutations in a gene. For a gene of 1000 amino acids, if there are 20 possible amino acids for

each position, then there are 20 000 possible amino acid variants for that gene. For a non-coding DNA segment of 1000 bases, there are 4000 possible variants for that segment. MAVEs and Massively Parallel Reporter Assays, or MPRA, are done to achieve this. Dr. Fowler, maybe you can explain more:

Doug Fowler: So both MPRA and deep mutational scanning use high throughput DNA sequencing to achieve the scale that they have and the way that works is actually pretty cool. We can have large libraries corresponding to thousands or tens of thousands of variants whose function we can assay by essentially using a DNA sequencer as a counter. And that library of genetic variant could be a library of enhancers or a library of proteins.

Evelina: An enhancer is a segment of DNA that controls the amount of protein that is made by the cell.

Doug Fowler: And in both cases, you rig up an assay such that the change in the variant function is linked to a change in something you can sequence with a high throughput DNA sequencer.

And in the case of MPRA, that's like a barcode that tells you that is a barcode that tells you how much transcription that particular variant drives. And in the case of a deep mutational scan, that can actually just be the protein sequence itself or it can be a barcode.

Kortni: DNA barcodes are very similar to barcodes you see at the store, for example. They are short DNA sequences that are unique, and they can be used to label and identify a gene. They are unique identifiers that allow scientists to 'count' how often a variant of interest does something.

Doug Fowler: But in either case, you're sort of counting up the number of times each variant appears in your assay, maybe it's before and after growth, maybe it's before and after protein binding. And then by doing math on those counts, those before and after counts, you can derive a score for every variant and that score tells you how that variant functioned in the assay.

Evelina: Dr. Fields, this idea was developed in your lab. Can you tell us how it all came together?

Stan Fields: It's an interesting story because it's a typical example of how in technology development, the work can meander and move and pivot and change from what you were initially trying to do towards something else. So when Doug came to the lab as a postdoc, he was working early on with a graduate student, Carlo Soraya and the project was a pretty ambitious project. What they had set out to do was to try to assay many different proteins, a large set of proteins, all at the same time and look at different functional activities of those proteins.

And the idea was that they would couple the DNAs that encoded these proteins onto a micro array, so initially a DNA microarray. And then use in vitro transcription and translation to make those proteins and have those proteins linked to the DNA that was coating them on the array, so it was now a protein array as well as a DNA array. Then we would look for activities that might be, say, binding to some probe or whatever, and then use DNA sequencing of the DNA on the array as the readout to know which proteins had that activity.

So that was the idea that they set out on, it was quite ambitious and they spent a period of months really going at it just trying to get the initial idea to work of being able to put down DNA onto the array and then get it to translate and make proteins. And despite a lot of good effort from the part of Doug and Carlos, we weren't really making that much headway on the project, and it was frustrating.

And I think sometime, probably somewhere in early 2009, Doug realized that what we were trying to do on this DNA microarray becoming a protein microarray could be done in a lot more easy fashion than what we're imagining. And what he came up with was just the idea of using phage display, which had been around for 20 plus years at that point to carry out that kind of assays that we wanted, which was basically to have some way where we could assay a protein for an activity and then have the genotype, the DNA couple to that present linked physically to the protein activity.

And I think once he proposed it, then everybody in the lab said of course, that it seems totally obvious we should be going that way. And most technology development I found always works that way: that new technology ideas once you have them, they seem totally obvious in retrospect, but still somebody had to come up with them and sort of prospect to do it.

Kortni: Dr. Fowler, when did you start thinking of this technology for clinical applications?

Doug Fowler: We talk a lot about using mutational scanning data to understand protein structure and function, to understand evolution and to engineer proteins and do all kinds of other stuff. And we taught, you know, sort of, yeah, also you could use it to understand human genetic variation. And wouldn't that be cool? You know, it's just been an incredibly satisfying thing to have this technology grow and become useful and become like immediately useful and get emails from clinicians being like, I know you're working on this gene, like, is it, is it done yet? Like do you know what this variant does? You know, the human genetics application was the one that maybe we most undersold as something that was really gonna, you know, change things. But it's been super exciting to be wrong in that way and still be part of, you know, making it happen.

Evelina: Can scientists make MAVEs for every gene?

Doug Fowler: Well, when technology is yoked to an important problem, the nature of technology is to grow, to get better. And so I think there's two key ways in which the technology will grow. The experimental technologies will come down in cost and consequently increase in scale and they will increasingly be focused in my opinion on context, right, so we're pretty good now, we have technologies that can measure generic properties like cell growth or protein abundance. And we also have predictive models that are really darn good at predicting generic functional is-nonfunctional variant effects. But if we want to think about designing or applying a treatment, you know, that might target a particular mechanism of pathogenicity. Well, we have to know that mechanism and currently, we can't really predict that effectively and we can't really do experiments at scale with some exceptions in that space either. It has to be said that we will not need to measure every last variant effect for every last context and every last mechanism. We will increasingly be playing a game of generating just enough functional data to drive good predictions and evaluate those predictions fairly.

Kortni: So the endpoint is not to measure all possible variants of all genes?

Doug Fowler: I think the end point is that we have a model that is based on all kinds of evidence, right, multiple sequence alignments, experiments, patient data and biobank data. We have a model, some kind of grand unifying model that gives us nucleotide resolution with mechanism. Deep, mechanistic insight for every variant in every gene in the human genome. I think that that is a realizable but ambitious endpoint, sure there are going to be some mechanisms we don't get and sure there are going to be some genes we don't get because we don't even know

their function still. But we can get pretty close to that and when we get there, I will feel satisfied that we've done our jobs.

Evelina: Is the scale of this challenge the reason why there is a need for an alliance for variant effects?

Doug Fowler: So the Atlas of Variant Effects Alliance is an international organization that we (Matt Hurles, Dave Adams, Lea Starita, J.T. Neal and some others) founded. And the idea of the Atlas of Variant Effects Alliance is to try to bring about an Atlas of variant effects. By that I mean at least for the human genome, and maybe for other genomes too, a comprehensive set of variant effect maps that collectively contain the effects of every possible single letter variant in every disease related gene in (at least) the human genome.

Kortni: How long has this alliance been working on this problem?

Doug Fowler: We founded the alliance at a meeting that happened in 2020; that was really a great meeting. I think there were about 100 people there, and they ranged from hardcore clinical variant interpretation-oriented clinicians, so clinical geneticists, to inveterate technology developers like me, to people who were interested in scaling to produce data, to people who are interested in learning how to use the data [such as] patients and patient advocates. All sorts of people were at that meeting and it was a really great discussion and I think the alliance really reflects that diversity of interests and opinions and is seeking to try to solve some of the key problems that we have as we are entering this world where we can generate variant effect data at the scale that is needed to actually make an Atlas.

Evelina: Promoting and doing this research requires a heroic amount of effort. How large is the team behind the alliance?

Doug Fowler: Nominally, there are about 500 people in the alliance at the moment, I would say that we have maybe 100 very active members who are working on one thing or another.

Kortni: Ultimately, will the alliance need to branch out and talk to clinicians, Dr. Fields?

Stan Fields: A part of that whole equation that's really maybe more difficult to solve is then how do you embed all of this data into the clinical community in a way that is understandable and interpretable by clinicians and have them be able to use this to advise patients on risks and diagnoses and so on.

And I think that component will require a lot of partnerships between the basic scientists who are doing these kinds of studies and the computational biologists who are building the predictors and then the clinicians who are going to have to interpret all of this for a huge number of different disease genes and a large patient population.

Kortni: Thank you Dr. Fields and Dr. Fowler for speaking with us today.

Evelina: Ultimately, we hope that the research we do can be used in the clinic. To learn more, we connected with Dr. Greg Costain from SickKids hospital to help us understand the impact of these mutations on our society.

Kortni: Thank you for joining us today, can you tell our listeners a little bit about yourself?

Greg Costain: I'm Greg Costain, I'm a medical genetics doctor at Sick Kids. I'm also a physician scientist. Being a medical geneticist means that I'm a rare disease doctor who's primarily tasked with meeting with families and facilitating their genomic centered care.

In my research lab, we focus largely on how we can improve genetics care through increasing access to genetics technologies like genome sequencing, interpreting the rare variation that we can find by genome sequencing and discovering new rare diseases.

Evelina: What is a rare disease, and how often do you find them?

Greg Costain: Usually a rare disease is defined based on its apparent prevalence within a population, so how many people within a given population are living with that particular condition at that moment.

Greg Costain: To give you some baseline numbers in the United States people often talk about a rare disease being something that affects fewer than 200,000 people in their country. In the European Union, and Here in Canada, we often talk about rare diseases being conditions that affect less than one in 2000 individuals. However, when we talk about the impact on a family, because there are many individuals within a family, it's not to imply that a rare disease is only impacting one in 2000 families. In fact, many of us are impacted by rare diseases, whether we appreciate it at the moment or not.

Kortni: If it's not 1 in 2000 families, how much is it?

Greg Costain: One of the challenges with developing new treatments for rare diseases is that rare diseases are so rare. Collectively, rare diseases are incredibly common. With some estimates being that up to one in 12 families may be impacted by a rare disease.

And yet many individual rare diseases are so rare that someone with a new diagnosis might be the only person in their city, or their province, or their country who so far has been identified as having that condition.

This challenges a lot of the models of drug development and therapeutic development that were previously the standard.

Evelina: This would imply that most of the listeners might have heard of some rare diseases. Can you provide some examples?

Greg Costain: In general, most rare diseases are probably not talked about enough. Some of the more common rare diseases that people may or may not be familiar with are named genetic conditions like Duchenne muscular dystrophy, cystic fibrosis. But in my world, as a medical geneticist, we routinely see conditions that are much less common or well recognized in the population.

Kortni: I understand that you study rare forms of epilepsy in your lab, what is the biological basis of this disease?

Greg Costain: The gene that's most commonly associated with severe epilepsy in children is called SCN1A. SCN1A encodes for a component of a neuronal sodium channel. And so it falls

within a category of conditions that are very relevant to my genetics practice called channelopathy. The SCN1A gene is usually associated with epilepsy through a loss of function mechanism. Most of us have two copies of this gene. And if you only have one functional copy of the gene, then you're at risk for having epilepsy and specifically a clinical syndrome of epilepsy called Dravet syndrome.

One of the challenges with diagnosing epilepsy caused by changes in the SCN1A gene is that there can be many different missense variants in the gene that are initially hard to interpret and as well, there's well known variability in the way in which changes in this gene can manifest in different individuals even within the same family.

Evelina: I see, so this probably makes it really difficult to diagnose. Can you tell us a bit about the challenges there?

Greg Costain: When you're living with a rare disease, we often hear from families about a diagnostic Odyssey that they might have been on, multiple specialists that they saw, and challenges in ultimately arriving at a specific diagnosis. They are very difficult to diagnose because many healthcare providers may not have previously seen a patient with that same condition and many of the rare diseases can resemble more common diseases or present with issues that are commonly seen in subspecialty clinics, accessing genetics care is a challenge in many parts of the world.

Kortni: Without revealing details about patients, can you explain the process of diagnosis when the disease you are facing is rare? I imagine that most diagnoses begin with the most prevalent disease which presents the symptoms that you observe. At which point do you say, OK, this is a rare genetic condition.

Greg Costain: In my clinical practice at SickKids, I'm often seeing children who have unexplained epilepsy or a severe developmental disability. One of the reasons that we have a dedicated genetics clinic focused on that population is because of what we've learned over the last few decades, about the causes of epilepsy in kids or severe developmental disability. Many children living with those conditions in our region have those conditions as a result of an underlying genetic difference or set of genetic differences, what we call DNA variants, they have rare genetic diseases that are the underlying explanation for those brain related symptoms. And so my jobs are often to either assess individuals and decide on the best options for them in terms

of clinical genetic testing, to see if we can identify or pinpoint a specific genetic cause or to help interpret the results of genetic testing that might have been ordered by another kind of health care provider or finally, to discuss with the family that we think we do have a diagnosis or explanation for a child's issues and to provide additional counseling and recommendations about how to care for that child.

Evelina: You mentioned earlier that there are ways of identifying the genetic basis of disease. How do you do this? How does it work?

Greg Costain: Our Ministry of Health as a primary funder for our health care system supports doing broad genetic testing for many of the children that we see at SickKids and other pediatric hospitals. In my practice, I'm routinely now arranging for advanced clinical genetic testing that's often performed in the province, that is looking across nearly all the DNA for differences that might be diagnostic or explanatory for a child's issues. Two of the most common genetic tests that I arranged in my practice are complementary to each other.

The most commonly ordered genetic tests right now in pediatrics in Ontario would be a chromosomal microarray test. This is a genome wide test that scans across almost all of the DNA to look for pieces missing, or pieces added to chromosomes or relative genomic imbalances, or copy number variation.

The other test that I'm commonly ordering in my clinical practice is genome-wide sequencing, either clinical exome sequencing or in fact, now genome sequencing for a small number of people, so essentially reading across nearly all the letters of the DNA to look for rare variants at the sequence level that might explain the child's issues .

Kortni: Sequencing a whole genome seems like an obvious solution to identifying the cause of the disease, if it is genetic. Is it really a silver bullet?

Greg Costain: Oftentimes the genetic testing that we do order for families can identify one or more changes in the DNA that are of uncertain significance. And so, for some families, even after having had them be identified as potentially having a rare disease and having been successful at finding ways for them to access clinical genetic testing. We're still left with residual uncertainty based on the result.

One of the biggest challenges that we see in clinical practice and in my research relates to variant interpretation. Our ability to sequence the genome and detect rare variants has far outpaced our ability to interpret them in a given clinical context. We need creative solutions and new strategies to try to interpret variants, including orthogonal experiments or orthogonal data that is not necessarily directly related to the factors that we've historically used to interpret rare variation. Briefly some of the factors that we have relied on historically act as heuristics or rules of thumb that can be useful for filtering variation or prioritizing variation.

Evelina: While an atlas for all disease genes seems far away, Dr. Costain sees a promising future for genetic diagnoses.

Greg Costain: The hope that we have with MAVEs or multiplex high throughput functional assays is that they're generating a complementary piece of evidence that can help us interpret more rare variants at a genome level scale.

This could help us in terms of interpreting specific variants we're seeing in patients and also help us with filtering and trying to discover a new genetic cause of illness through our manipulation of very large genetic data sets.

Kortni: And can this lead to a cure? Dr. Costain, do you think this is actually happening?

Greg Costain: Proof of concept exists for precision therapy development in the form of anti-sense oligonucleotide-type treatments for patients with certain specific variants causing certain rare diseases. At SickKids, my colleagues have shown again as a proof of concept that it was possible to develop a gene therapy for a specific child. After diagnosing this family's child with a rare progressive brain disease, and recognizing that one of the two DNA variants that was causing the disease in this child was a variant deep within an intron that was potentially amenable to splice-switching antisense oligonucleotide therapy. Amazingly, this team was able to develop an anti-sense oligonucleotide therapy, test it pre-clinically, receive regulatory approval, and administer this treatment to the child in a span of about eighteen months.

Kortni: Thank you for joining us today Dr. Costain.

Alex: Today, we discovered what a DNA variant is, the difficulties of interpreting these variants and how large-scale experiments can provide important information to drive rare disease

therapies. If you would like to know more about the efforts to solve these variants of uncertain significance you can find more information from the Atlas of Variant Effects Alliance.

Evelina: Before we go, we have asked some rapid-fire questions to all three of our guests.

Moez Dawood: Alright, DNA or RNA?

Stan Fields: DNA

Doug Fowler: DNA

Moez: R or Python?

Stan Fields: Python

Doug Fowler: Python

Moez: Short-read or Long-read?

Stan Fields: Short-read

Doug Fowler: Short-read!

Moez: Single-Cell or Bulk?

Stan Fields: Bulk

Doug Fowler: Bulk

Greg Costain: Bulk sequencing

Moez: Knock-in or Knock-out?

Stan Fields: Knock out

Doug Fowler: Knock in

Moez: Golden Gate or Gibson?

Stan Fields: Gibson

Doug Fowler: Golden Gate

Greg Costain: Gibson

Moez: Coding or Noncoding?

Stan Fields: Coding for sure

Doug Fowler: Coding

Moez: In vitro or in vivo?

Stan Fields: In vivo

Doug Fowler: Im going to say cells are good enough

Moez: Favorite model organism?

Stan Fields: Yeast

Doug Fowler: Yeast

Greg Costain: Humans!

Moez: Favorite scientist?

Stan Fields: Fred Sanger

Doug Fowler: Barbara McClintock

Moez: Favorite media?

Stan Fields: YEPD, it's a yeast media

Doug Fowler: DMEM

Moez: Favorite sequencing technology?

Stan Fields: Dideoxy sequencing

Moez: Favorite piece of lab equipment?

Stan Fields: PCR machine

Doug Fowler: The pipette

Moez: Favorite science movie/media?

Stan Fields: Gattaca

Doug Fowler: The Adventures of Buckaroo Banzai Across the 8th dimension

Greg Costain: Star Wars, though obviously not a science-focused movie, has a creativity and speaks to a diversity in terms of the universe that I can appreciate in the context of then studying the universe in the form of a single genome.

Moez: Something outside the lab that you wish you could multiplex?

Stan Fields: Reading and writing

Doug Fowler: Cooking

Greg Costain: Childcare challenges that we have at home.

Moez: What is the smartest thing you've done in the lab?

Stan Fields: Probably the first yeast two-hybrid experiment.

Doug Fowler: My lab has recently just disposed of all types of cloning, and we only do golden gate cloning, and that was very smart.

Moez: Then the last question here, what is the stupidest thing you've ever done in the lab?

Stan Fields: That's easy, I set fire to my lab bench as a student and I did it on the day that I was planning to ask the professor overseeing the lab for a letter of reference.

Doug Fowler: One thing that I did, was try to use a hydrogenator, definitely one night late in lab. I managed to pop the top off of this thing, so that oxygen mixed in there and it just instantly caught fire.

Moez: We appreciate your time, thank you so much.

Alex: Tune in next time on Variants and Us, where we will discuss the rare mutations responsible for skin cancers.

[Outro music]

Variant Effect What? Episode 1 Show Notes

Further reading on rare disease incidence and classification:

Groft, S. C.; Posada, M.; Taruscio, D. Progress, Challenges and Global Approaches to Rare Diseases. *Acta Paediatr.* 2021, 110 (10), 2711–2716. DOI: 10.1111/apa.15974

Richter, T.; Nestler-Parr, S.; Babela, R.; Khan, Z. M.; Tesoro, T.; Molsen, E.; Hughes, D. A. Rare Disease Terminology and Definitions—A Systematic Global Review: Report of the ISPOR Rare Disease Special Interest Group. *Value Health* 2015, 18 (6), 906–914. DOI: 10.1016/j.jval.2015.05.008

Deep mutational scanning work done by Dr. Fields and Dr. Fowler:

Fowler, D. M.; Fields, S. Deep Mutational Scanning: A New Style of Protein Science. *Nat. Methods* 2014, 11 (8), 801–807. DOI: 10.1038/nmeth.3027

Further reading on MAVEs as well as the Atlas of Variant Effects Alliance:

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